

with 10 and 20 t FYM/ha were 0.52 and 0.76 t/ha, respectively. Highest yield was with 20 t FYM and 20 kg N/ha.

The residual effect of FYM on the following rapeseed crop was significant.

Rapeseed yields were 0.17 and 0.24 t/ha higher with 10 and 20 t FYM/ha, respectively. The residual effect of fertilizer N on rapeseed yield was not significant.

Applying 20 kg N with 20 t FYM/ha to spring rice not only increased rice yield, but also doubled yield of the succeeding rapeseed crop. □

Disease management

Field evaluation of fungicides to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

Y. Suryadi and T. S. Kadir, Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops, West Java, Indonesia

We tested eight fungicides against *Rhizoctonia solani* in the field.

Pelita I-2 was planted in a randomized block design with three replications in 4- × 5-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plants were artificially inoculated 55 d after transplanting (DT) by placing small amounts of ShB inoculum on rice husk at the center of each hill. Fungicides were sprayed at 60, 67, and 74 DT, and disease incidence (lesion length and relative lesion height)

Control of rice ShB by fungicides. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1986-87.^a

Treatment	Application rate (formulation/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Lesion length (cm)	RLN ^b (%)	Severity ^c (%)
Benomyl	0.25 kg	124.16 a	58.26 cde	46.94 bc	39.14 cd
Mancozeb	2.0 kg	125.16 a	49.08 abcd	39.21 ab	26.37 abc
PCNB	1.0 kg	123.59 a	52.89 bcd	42.72 abc	35.60 bcd
Chlorothalonil	1.7 kg	125.34 a	46.06 ab	36.77 ab	22.12 ab
Carbendazim	0.8 kg	125.91 a	56.07 bcde	44.52 abc	33.53 bcd
Triazole	0.5 liter	116.77 b	40.13 a	34.16 a	19.5 a
Captafol	1.5 liter	123.51 ab	59.23 c	46.14 bc	39.74 cd
Maneb + zineb	1.0 kg	121.6 ab	47.69 abc	39.15 ab	26.30 abc
Control (unsprayed)	—	126.69 a	65.78 e	51.92 c	48.8 d
CV (%)		3.01	11.29	11.07	14.41

^aMean of 3 replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bRLH = $\frac{\text{lesion length}}{\text{plant height}} \times 100$

^cSeverity = $\frac{0 (n_0) + 1 (n_1) + 5 (n_3) + 20 (n_5) + 50 (n_7) + 100 (n_9)}{\text{number of tillers observed}} \times 100$

n0 - n9 = number of tillers with 0-9 scale.

measured 25 d after flowering.

Triazole was most effective in inhibiting enlargement of ShB lesions. Significant lesion reduction also

occurred with chlorothalonil, mancozeb, and maneb + zineb treatments (see table). No phytotoxicity occurred in any treatment. □

Survival of rice root-knot nematode juveniles in moist soil

M. H. Soomro, Agriculture Department, University of Reading, Reading, United Kingdom (present address: Crop Diseases Research Institute, National Agricultural Research Centre, Park Road, Islamabad, Pakistan)

Severe infestations of the soil by *Meloidogyne graminicola* can cause up to 50% yield losses. To develop an efficient control method for this nematode we need to know its survival capacity in the absence of a host plant.

To measure rice root-knot nematode survival, eight plastic pots were filled with sterilized soil and inoculated with 4,000 freshly hatched *M. graminicola* juveniles/pot. The soil was kept moist. Pots were incubated at two

Nematodes surviving soil incubation and infesting host plant roots. Reading, UK.

Soil incubation period (mo)	Survival (no./g roots)	
	26±4°C	20±1°C
2	442	812
3	133	693
4	96	451
5	536	707

temperatures: four pots at 26 ± 4 °C, and four pots at 20 ± 1 °C.

Survival and viability of the nematodes were measured by a bioassay method at 2, 3, 4, and 5 mo after inoculation. After assay, a 2-wk-old seedling of *Echinochloa colona* was planted in one pot from each incubation temperature and kept at 26 ± 4 °C.

Seedlings were uprooted 2 mo after transplanting. Roots washed free from soil were weighed and fixed in FA 4:1.

Fixed roots were stained in acid fuchsin in lacto-glycerol and cleared for 24 h. Number of nematodes in the roots was estimated by counting nematodes in three 0.5-g subsamples (see table).

Second stage juvenile of rice root-knot nematodes can survive in soil without any host plant for up to 5 mo at temperatures up to 26°C and remain viable to invade host roots and reproduce. □

Recovery of rice tungro virus (RTV) from rice stubble

Z. M. Flores, E. R. Tiongco, R. C. Cabunagan, and H. Hibino, IRRI

Rice stubble can serve as a RTV source. In a greenhouse study, stubble of IR22 and IR36 naturally infected with both